

An Optimized Electric Power and Reserves Economic Dispatch Algorithm for Isolated Systems Considering Water Inflow Management

D. Ferreira-Martínez

Departament of Particle Physics
Santiago de Compostela University
Santiago de Compostela, Spain
dario.ferreira@rai.usc.es

Filipe Tadeu Oliveira

Centre for Power and Energy Systems
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal
filipe.oliveira@inesctec.pt

F. J. Soares

Centre for Power and Energy Systems
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal
filipe.j.soares@inesctec.pt

C. L. Moreira

Centre for Power and Energy Systems
INESC TEC
Porto, Portugal
carlos.moreira@inesctec.pt

Rui Martins

EEM
Empresa de Eletricidade da Madeira
Madeira, Portugal
rmartins@eem.pt

Abstract—While the share of renewable energy in interconnected systems has been increasing steadily, in isolated systems it represents a bigger challenge. This paper presents a dispatch algorithm integrating thermal, wind, solar and hydro generation and storage for an isolated network, which allows maximizing renewable energy integration and reducing the share of thermal energy in the mix. The possibility of using the battery to provide “spinning” reserve is also considered. The algorithm was tested and validated using real data from the island of Madeira, Portugal. Results prove the robustness and flexibility of the algorithm, showing that a significant decrease in the thermal fraction is achievable, and that it is possible to accommodate an increase in renewable generation with minimal or no curtailment at all.

Index Terms—energy and reserve dispatch, water management, renewable power generation, hydro pumping, storage, isolated system

NOMENCLATURE

Technology related parameters

$Demand_k$ [MW]. Power demand in time “k”.

Eff_g [0 to 1]. If generator “g” is a pump, it indicates its efficiency (potential energy of the pumped water/energy used to pump the water).

$Inflow_{s,k}$ [MWh]. Water inflow from natural sources (rivers, rain, springs) that arrive to reservoir “s” during time-step “k”.

$InitialLevel_s$ [0 to 1]. Indicates the proportion of the reservoir capacity that is filled at the beginning of the modeled period.

$MinOp_g$ [%]. Operational minimum of technology “g” with respect to its maximum power. Used for thermal generators.

$Output_g$ [0 or 1]. Indicates if a generator produces energy when operating or not. It is 1 in case of real generators

and 0 otherwise.

$PfromS_{g,s,dt}$ [0 or 1]. Indicates if the generator “g” receives water from the reservoir “s” “dt” time-steps later. In the instantaneous case, $dt=0$.

$Pmax_g$ [MW]. Maximum power of generator “g”. Used to limit the power production, pump capacity or water flow.

$Pmin_{g,k}$ [MW]. Minimum power at which generator “g” must work in the time “k”. Used to model water consumption (voiding the associated reservoir) for human consumption, agriculture and ecological flows.

$PrimCapDown_g$ [%]. % of the Online Capacity that can be provided as downward reserves.

$PrimCapUp_g$ [%]. % of the Online Capacity that can be provided as upward reserves.

$PrimDownDemand_k$ [MW]. Downward reserve power demand in time “k”.

$PrimUpDemand_k$ [MW]. Upward reserve power demand in time “k”.

$ProdCost_g$ [EUR/MWh]. Indicates the generator production cost.

$PtoS_{g,s,dt}$ [0 or 1]. Indicates if the generator “g” provides water to the reservoir “s” after a time “dt”. It is used both for pumps and for water flows from one reservoir to another. The set “dt” allows to consider delays in the water flow from one reservoir to other.

$Pump_g$ [0 or 1]. Indicates if generator “g” is a pump (1) or not (0). If it is a pump, it consumes energy when in operation.

$RampDown_g$ [%Pmax/minute]. Maximum power decrease from one time step to the next one as a % of the maximum power (Pmax).

$RampUp_p_g$ [%Pmax/minute]. Maximum power increase from one time step to the next one as a % of the maximum power (Pmax).

$RenewableResource_k$ [MW]. Renewable power available.

$Smax_g$ [MWh]. Maximum storage capacity of reservoir "s".

ts [%]. Time-step used, expressed as roportion of an hour.

Variables

$OnlineCapacity_{g,k}$ [MW]. Amount of operative capacity of "g" in time "k". This capacity represents the amount of total generators on, used specifically to model the fossil generators.

$p_{g,k}$ Active power of generator "g" in time-step "k". It is used to represent an energy production or a water flow (in terms of energy).

$PrimDown_{g,k}$ [MW]. Amount of downward primary reserve provided by generator "g" in time "k".

$PrimUp_{g,k}$ [MW]. Amount of upward primary reserve provided by generator "g" in time "k".

$SLevel_{s,k}$ Amount of water (in terms of energy) stored in reservoir "s" in time-step "k".

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition towards sustainable energy systems has become an urgent matter given the pressing need to mitigate climate change and to reduce global dependency of fossil fuels.

Madeira, an island located in the Atlantic Ocean, faces increased energy challenges due to its geographical characteristics and isolated electric power system, which relies heavily on fossil fuel-based generation to satisfy the demand and ensure appropriate network resiliency levels. As a result, there is a growing interest by the regional authorities in increasing the installed power and the share of renewable energy generation in the electricity mix.

The complex hydroelectric system of the island takes particular importance under these circumstances, as it may act as an energy buffer that stores energy when renewable sources are abundant and delivers it when needed. However, the complex interactions and dependencies of generation, demand and storage assets in the island require effective tools to optimize system performance and ensure a proficient use of the hydroelectric assets.

While specific tools are required to address these complexities, a wide range of efforts have been done in energy-water systems and hybrid renewable energy systems so far. A compilations of these tools can be seen in [1] and [2], exemplifying the high diversity of this type of models in terms of approach, time scale, represented phenomena, and methodology. These works are particularly important in islands, where stability and energy dispatch is fundamental because of the high variability of renewable resources and power demand due to the small size of the system. Some examples in this direction are the works of [3] and [4]. However, models found lack important aspects needed to the specific problem of Madeira island, by not modelling energy dispatch, storage facilities or cascade hydro power with sufficient detail.

This work focuses on developing a comprehensive mathematical model to represent Madeira's electric and hydro systems, taking into account the technical characteristics of the generation and storage technologies available, as well as the electricity demand fluctuations. In particular, the model considers the detailed characteristics of the island's hydro systems, which is composed of several generators, pumps and a complex system of interconnected reservoirs. An optimization problem using the model was formulated to perform a day-ahead energy dispatch with an efficient water management, with the goal of maximizing renewable energy utilization and minimizing overall electricity production costs.

The methodology developed in this work is described in section II. Section III describes the Madeira Island case study, while the results obtained after solving the optimization problem are presented and discussed in section IV. The main conclusions achieved and future work in prospect are presented in section V.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed model is based on the work presented in [5], and its formulation using PuLP as in [6], by adapting the proposed method to sequential time, cascade hydro-power, and other specific needs of the problem. The model describes Madeira's electric and hydro system as a set of generators (g), that can produce or transform energy, and a set of reservoirs (s), that can store it. The set of generators includes thermal units (which produce electricity but are not associated to any reservoir), hydro turbines (producing electricity while voiding a reservoir), hydro pumps (using electricity to move water from a reservoir to another, downstream to upstream) or flows of water (modelled as virtual generators, voiding water from reservoirs without electricity production). The latter are used to model waterways connecting reservoirs that have no generation capability or water used for human and agriculture consumption, in which case a minimum flow is mandatory and specified). All generators have a maximum power limit and all reservoirs have a maximum capacity for water storage. Water flows and stored water are described in terms of power/energy, taking into account conversion factors that relate the water content and the potential energy production when turbined.

The system aims to optimize the energy dispatch, at minimum cost and increasing renewable energy penetration, while satisfying electricity demand, spinning reserve requirements and the water needed for human consumption, agriculture and ecological flows.

Python and PuLP were used to build and solve the optimization problem. In subsections A and B, a detailed description of the variables and parameters used is provided, followed by the mathematical formulation of the model in subsection C.

A. Model

Equation (1) represents the balance of energy, equalizing production to the power demand (including pumps consump-

tion).

$$\sum_g p_{g,k} \times \text{Output}_g = \text{Demand}_k + \sum_g p_{g,k} \times \text{Pump}_g / \text{Eff}_g \quad (1)$$

Equations (2) and (3) represent the maximum and minimum limits for each generator in each time-step. These equations are also used for virtual generators, to represent the minimum water flows required for human consumption, agriculture and ecological flows.

$$p_{g,k} \leq \text{Pmax}_{g,k} \quad (2)$$

$$p_{g,k} \geq \text{Pmin}_{g,k} \quad (3)$$

Equation (4) defines the amount of renewable energy not used. This variable is used in the optimization function to "encourage" storage devices to absorb renewable production in excess.

$$\text{RewLose} = \sum_{g, \text{Rew}_g=1} (\text{Pmax}_{g,k} - p_{g,k}) \quad (4)$$

Equation (5) indicates the initial level of each storage.

$$SLevel(s, \min_k) = \text{Smax}_s \times \text{InitialLevel}_s \quad (5)$$

Equation (6) represents the state of charge of the storage in each time-step. It relates the state of charge of the previous time-step with the amount of energy voided (through turbines or for human use) and received (through pumping or arriving from upstream reservoirs) during that time. Index "kk" is used to account energy that was turbined in previous time steps, but that can arrive a time k-kk later.

$$SLevel(s, k+1) = SLevel_{s,k} - \sum_g p_{g,k} \times (\text{PfromS}_{g,s} \times \text{ts} + \sum_{\substack{ss, kk \\ kk < k \\ k-kk < \max(dt)}} p_{g, kk} \times \text{PtoS}_{g,s, k-kk} \times \text{ts} + \text{Inflow}_{s,k}) \quad (6)$$

Equations (7), (8), (9), and (10) ensure that the storage level never surpasses the maximum storage capacity nor decreases below zero. Specifically, (9) and (10) ensure that the limitation applies to the end of the modelled period. Equation (10) force the storage level at the end of the modelled period to be equal to the initial level, ensuring an equilibrium in storage use.

$$SLevel_{s,k} \leq \text{Smax}_s \quad (7)$$

$$SLevel_{s,k} \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$SLevel(s, \max(k)) - \sum_g p_{g,k} \times (\text{PfromS}_{g,s} \times \text{ts} + \sum_{\substack{ss, kk \\ kk < k \\ k-kk < \max(dt)}} p_{g, kk} \times \text{PtoS}_{g,s, k-kk} \times \text{ts} + \text{Inflow}_{s,k}) \leq \text{Smax}_s \quad (9)$$

$$SLevel(s, \max(k)) - \sum_g p_{g,k} \times (\text{PfromS}_{g,s} \times \text{ts} + \sum_{\substack{ss, kk \\ kk < k \\ k-kk < \max(dt)}} p_{g, kk} \times \text{PtoS}_{g,s, k-kk} \times \text{ts} + \text{Inflow}_{s,k}) \geq \text{Smax}_s \times \text{InitialLevel}_s \quad (10)$$

Equations (11) to (17) are reserve-related and were adapted from [7]. Equations (11) and (12) ensure that a minimum amount of upward and downward reserve must be available in the system.

$$\sum_g \text{PrimUp}_{p_{g,k}} \geq \text{PrimUpDemand}_{g,k} \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_g \text{PrimDown}_{g,k} \geq \text{PrimDownDemand}_{g,k} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{Online}_{g,k} \leq \text{Pmax}_g \quad (13)$$

Equations (14) and (15) quantify and limit the upward reserve. Equation (14) indicates the amount of reserve is proportional to the online capacity, as the formulation considers that the amount of generators working increase with the amount of online capacity (and if more generators are active, more can change production simultaneously). Equation (15) indicates that the amount of upward reserve is limited by the difference between the maximum power of the online generators and the power that is already being used.

$$\text{PrimUp}_{p_{g,k}} \leq \text{PrimCapUp}_g \times \text{Online}_g \quad (14)$$

$$p_{g,k} + \text{PrimUp}_{p_{g,k}} \leq \text{Online}_{g,k} \quad (15)$$

Equations (16) and (17) quantify and limit the downward reserve. Equation (16) works similarly to equation (14). Equation (17) considers the effect of operational minimum, indicating that the total downward reserve is not the total production of the technology, but the difference between that and the technical minimum of operation.

$$\text{PrimDown}_{g,k} \leq \text{PrimCapDown}_g \times \text{Online}_g \quad (16)$$

$$p_{g,k} \geq \text{PrimDown}_{g,k} + \text{MinOp}_g \times \text{Online}_{g,k} \quad (17)$$

For the case where a storage service can provide reserve, two additional restrictions must be considered. Firstly, a storage device can provide downward reserve by taking energy when it is not already scheduled to do so during dispatch and there is enough capacity in the battery or reservoir to receive this energy, as represented by (18); and secondly, it can provide upward reserve only while it has enough energy stored to do so (19). These equations only apply if the generator provides energy to or extracts energy from a storage device. Similarly, (17) does not apply in the case of a charging device. Therefore, (17), (18), and (19) are conditional equations.

$$p_{g,k} + \text{PrimDown}_{g,k} \leq \sum_{g, \text{PtoS}_{g,s,0} >= 1} (\text{Smax}_s - SLevel_{s,k}) / \text{Eff}_g / \text{ts} \quad (18)$$

$$p_{g,k} + PrimUp_{p_{g,k}} \leq \sum_{g, P_{from} S_{g,s} \geq 1} SLevel_{s,k} / ts \quad (19)$$

Equations (20) and (21) limit the power ramp between time-steps, indicating the maximum ramp-up and ramp-down, respectively.

$$p_{g,k} - p_{g,k-1} \leq \mathbf{RampUp}_g \times ts \times \mathbf{Pmax}_g \times 60 \quad (20)$$

$$p_{g,k-1} - p_{g,k} \leq \mathbf{RampDown}_g \times ts \times \mathbf{Pmax}_g \times 60 \quad (21)$$

The objective function to minimize is the overall production costs, adding a term to induce minimization of curtailment and a penalization for voiding the storage, necessary to avoid simultaneous charge/discharge:

$$OF = \sum_k \left(\sum_g (\mathbf{ProdCost}_g + e) \times p_{g,k} + \mathbf{P} \times RewLose_k + \sum_{\substack{g,s \\ Pump_g=0 \\ P_{from} S_{g,s}=1 \\ Smax_s > 0}} (\mathbf{VP} \times p_{g,k}) \right) \times ts \quad (22)$$

where e is a small enough number, P is the penalization for curtailment (which should be smaller than production costs) and VP is the penalization for voiding the storage capacity, (which should be higher than curtailment penalization, but lower than production costs).

III. CASE STUDY

Madeira is a natural island, and its electrical network is also an isolated network, vertically integrated, operated by a public operator, Empresa Eletricidade da Madeira - EEM, which also holds most of the generation. In 2023, installed capacity was of 379.42 MW, peak load was 153.59 MW and total electricity production amounted to 897.90 GWh, of which 3.24 GWh were used for pumping, battery storage and synchronous compensation [8]. Most of the electricity produced comes from thermal groups (fuel oil and natural gas), but hydro, wind, solar PV and solid waste also contribute to the generation mix. Hydro power is mainly provided by two cascade water systems, Calheta and Serra de Água-Socorridos, both of which also have pumping capability. Their key parameters are indicated in Table I. For simplicity, thermal generators were considered as a single generator, comprising the summed capacity of all individual groups, as summarized in Table II. The system has also a lithium ion battery, as presented in Table III. Only thermal generators and the battery are considered for the provision of (upward and downward) spinning reserve, observing the n-1 criterion. As expressed in (15) and (17), the maximum power for upward reserve only considers online generators and the minimum power limiting downward reserve is not zero, but the technical operational minimum of the online generators.

Data used in this study for power demand and generation are real data for January 2022 - for readability reasons, only the first 10 days are shown in Fig. 1, in average hourly resolution.

Upward and downward primary reserve are set to 15 MW, the peak power provided by the largest thermal generator usually operating.

Each storage reservoir is initially at 30% of its capacity, and the model is forced to end with the same level, ensuring a balance between the water used and recovered.

The model will solve the dispatch problem for three scenarios, and compare the results with the actual dispatch/load of January 2022:

- **Standard scenario (STD).** The same conditions of January 2022 are considered.
- **Increased renewable energy scenario (REW).** An increase of 33% in wind power and of 100% in solar power is considered with respect to the STD scenario.
- **Increased renewable energy scenario + battery reserve (BAT).** Conditions of REW are maintained, but the consequences of using the battery for primary upward and downward reserve are evaluated.

IV. RESULTS

Table IV shows a comparison of the total electricity generation, by technology, produced in each scenario. "Hydro" includes Calheta, Serra de Água-Socorridos, and the run-of-river mini-hydro groups; "Renew" includes wind and solar energy; "Batt" is the amount of energy received from the battery; "Curtl" represents the curtailment from renewable energy and waste; and "Pump" is the energy used to pump water. Fig. 1 shows the electricity dispatch for the first ten days of the month in the different scenarios in hourly resolution.

Fig. 1 illustrates the behaviour of the model in the different scenarios and when compared to the actual data. It is able to dispatch the available resources, follow the load and use the hydro resources effectively in the periods of lower availability of renewables, while avoiding its use otherwise. A significant reduction in thermal generation is thus obtained in all of the scenarios optimized by the model. In the STD scenario, this is achieved by avoiding curtailment and improving storage management (both pumping and battery use are increased). Thermal generation is further reduced in the REW scenario, which also shows a higher increase in hydro-power and battery power to supply load due to the use of storage. However, despite the considerable use of renewable energy, this scenario cannot avoid the curtailment of some of the renewable resource, which increases when compared with the standard scenario, probably due to the limitations in the storage devices in some specific hours of high renewable production and low demand, but also due to the dispatch of thermal units for reserve. Further thermal generation is reduced in the scenario where the battery is allowed to provide "spinning" reserve. In this scenario (BAT), despite the increase of installed renewable energy, the curtailment is avoided thanks to the better adaption of the thermal generation, which in some periods is no longer required (even if at a technical minimum) for reserve purposes.

TABLE I
CASCADE HYDRO SYSTEM

	Water to Energy Value (MWh/d3)	Capacity (MWh)	Power (MW)	Pump	Inflow per hour (MWh)	Provides water to
Calheta hydro system						
Rocha Vermelha	0.40	0.020	0.75	No	0.5	Lev. Lombo Salão
Rabaçal	0.69	0.035	0.58	No	0.26	Lev. Lombo Salão
Paúl	1.45	14.455	No	0.18 MW 75% eff	0.1	Pico da Urze
Pico da Urze	1.45	1246.000	30	No	1.21	Lev. Lombo Salão
Lev. Lombo Salão	1.34	0	No	No	-0.27 ^a	Calheta II, Coruchéu or human consumption lev.
Coruchéu	1.45	98.292	No	16.5 MW 69% eff	0	Pico da Urze
Calheta II	1.34	26.8	7	No	0	Sea
Serra de Água-Socorridos hydro system						
Serra de Água	0.94	18.8	10.8	No	1.7	Canal do Norte
Tunel Encumeada	1	24.97	No	No	0.81	Canal do Norte
Canal do Norte	1	19.47	No	No	0	Socorridos
Socorridos	1	84.44	No or 24	No	0	Socorridos reservoir or human consumption lev.
Socorridos reservoir	1	32.174	No	11.3 MW 75% eff	0	Socorridos

^aThe negative inflow corresponds to human and agriculture water demand.

Fig. 1. Energy dispatch for first ten days of the modelled period.

TABLE II
THERMAL GENERATION

	Max Power (MW)	Op Min	PrimUp	PrimDown
Thermal generators	205.7	30%	1	1

TABLE III
BATTERY

	Capacity (MWh)	Power (MW)	PrimUp	PrimDown
Battery	16.4	15	1	1

A decrease in the use of storage devices is also observed, which can be explained because the reserve provided by the battery makes thermal generation dispensable, decreasing overall generation and the excess of energy, in the periods with high renewable resource. Fig. 2 depicts the evolution of "excess" power/energy (defined as non dispatchable sources + thermal technical minimum - load) throughout the first ten days of January 2022, as well as the energy which is used to charge storage systems and that is obtained from them. It helps to confirm the prior observation that having the battery providing reserves allows reducing both overall energy demand and curtailment, leading to a more energy-efficient (and economic) dispatch.

Fig. 2. Storage charge/discharge behaviour during first ten days of the modelled period for REW (left) and BAT (right) scenarios. The red line represents the excess of energy in the system; blue line represents the energy being stored (either in the battery or by pumping); and the green line represents the energy used from storage (Li-ion + hydro).

Regarding thermal generation from fossil fuels, the STD, REW and BAT optimized scenarios allow a reduction of 13.1%, 25.8%, and 28.4%, respectively, when compared to 2022 data. The reduction of greenhouse gases emissions are of the same order.

TABLE IV
ENERGY USE COMPARISON IN THE DIFFERENT SCENARIOS

GWh	Therm	Waste	Renew	Hydro	Batt	Curtl	Pump
2022	43.89	3.92	17.16	8.40	0.00	1.24	0.16
STD	38.13	3.92	18.40	8.54	0.26	0.00	0.91
REW	32.58	3.71	24.46	9.23	0.30	0.74	1.91
BAT	31.42	3.92	24.99	8.31	0.01	0.00	0.57

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an innovative dispatch algorithm integrating and optimizing electricity generation, storage and water management was presented and described in detail. It was then applied to the Madeira island case study, yielding better results from an economic and environmental viewpoint than those observed in the test period, considering the base case (STD). Tested with several scenarios with different levels of renewable generation, load and water inflow, the algorithm proved flexible and robust, which also converts it into a planning aid tool that can assist decision-makers in comparing alternatives to future expansions towards a green energy transition.

It is also clear from the case study analysis that despite increasing renewable energy penetration, upgraded hydro facilities and use of storage, Madeira's power system is presently still very much dependent on thermal generation from fossil fuels. However, for future prospect scenarios (REW and BAT) that include a further increase in wind, solar and hydro generation, results show that thermal generation reduction is achievable, particularly when using the battery as a provider of reserve, and also eliminating renewable energy curtailment.

Future work will include expanding the time frame of the present study and considering additional scenarios with a further increase in renewable energy sources and storage systems. Integration of this work with a water management algorithm is also planned.

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